

Short communication

Role of sex and route of administration in determining LD₅₀ of λ - cyhalothrin in Wistar rats

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Abstract

Female Wistar rats were more susceptible than males to cyhalothrin toxicity. The LD₅₀ in oral route was less (male - 75.85 mg/kg b. wt., female - 56.69 mg/kg b. wt.) than dermal route (male - 524.80 mg/kg b. wt., female - 426.58 mg/kg b. wt.).

Key words: Rats, λ - cyhalothrin, LD₅₀, sex difference.

λ - cyhalothrin is a wide spectrum nonsystemic cyanide containing pyrethroid insecticide with contact and stomach actions and repellent properties. It gives a rapid knock down effect and long residual activity. In the present investigation the LD₅₀ was evaluated in either sex of Wistar rats by oral and dermal routes to study the sex bias and effects of route of administration.

One hundred and forty adult Wistar rats (male: 70, female: 70) weighing 180-200 g were used. These were provided standard diet and water *ad libitum* and housed under standard management practices. These were divided into 20 groups (10 groups each of males and females), each consisting of 7 individuals. Standard solution of λ - cyhalothrin was prepared by dissolving in groundnut oil. LD₅₀ was determined following standard method. Different doses were administered orally (20, 40, 80, 160 and 320 mg/kg b. wt.) and dermally (100, 200, 400, 800 and 1600 mg/kg b. wt.). The mortality and survival numbers of rats were recorded for each dose after 96 hours. The data were analysed statistically by log dose / probit regression line method (Finney, 1971).

The survival percentage showed a corresponding decrease with increasing dose of λ - cyhalothrin. The toxicity evaluation of λ - cyhalothrin to Wistar rats

(male and female) by oral and dermal route have been depicted in Table 1.

Table 1. Toxicity evaluation of λ - cyhalothrin in different sex by oral and dermal route.

Route	Sex	Regression equation	LD ₅₀ (mg/kg b. wt.)
Oral	Male	Y = 5.00 + 2.286 (X-1.88)	75.85
	Female	Y = 5.39 + 1.753 (X-1.92)	56.69
Dermal	Male	Y = 4.90 + 2.900 (X-2.90)	524.80
	Female	Y = 5.06 + 2.160 (X-2.66)	426.58

The LD₅₀ calculated by the two methods in either sex was different. The females have been found to be more susceptible than males. These findings supported the work of Raghavan and Dutta (1977). Gupta (1990) also reported that female rats and mice are more susceptible to cypermethrin toxicity. Young and Susick (1996) observed that liver toxicity is more in females than male rats and liver damage may be a reason for higher susceptibility of females, because liver is the site of detoxification. Ahmed and Gupta (1998) observed lower fertility index in females (65) than males (72) after cypermethrin (7.5 mg/kg b. wt.) intoxication in rats. The role of sex hormones might also be influencing the sex susceptibility but needs further elucidation. Further, the observed difference in LD₅₀ by the two routes (oral and dermal) is due to absorption phenomenon, which is faster with oral than

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the dermal route (Wilkinson, 1979). Thus, it is concluded that females are more susceptible than males to cyhalothrin toxicity and the LD₅₀ in oral route is less than dermal route.

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